

EFFECT OF EXTREME TEMPERATURES ON MICRO-DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN CF/POLYIMIDE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

CF Thorne® T650 8-harness satin weave fabric composite with thermosetting polyimide NEXIMID® MHT-R resin designed for high service temperatures is produced at around 390°C and therefore high thermal stresses develop after cooling down to room temperature. Thermal transverse stresses in bundles/layers are tensile and lead to multiple intra-bundle /intra-laminar cracking. When the composite plate is subjected to large and repeated temperature variations, new cracks can appear due to thermally induced fatigue stress. Experimental results show that the highest temperature in the cycle, where thermal stresses are low, has a significant detrimental effect on thermal fatigue resistance. Another observed phenomenon is thermal aging: at high temperature the mechanical properties are degrading with time. Aging and fatigue effects were separately analyzed for quasi-isotropic laminates with lay-up [(+45/-45)/(90/0)]_{2s}.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing interest of aerospace industry in composite materials has motivated the researchers to constantly investigate this research area in order to improve and develop new composites for specific applications. Composites are lightweight materials with excellent specific stiffness and strength. Some components require additional specific properties for their materials to be suitable for the environment in which it would be placed. The composites designated to aero-engine application, for example, need to perform well at high temperatures. The thermal fatigue and the long exposure to elevated temperatures can cause changes in the morphology, strength and stiffness. Therefore understanding the behavior of a composite material in this type of environment is of great importance.

Many researches have studied the thermal stability of the composite by quantifying the effect of the thermal fatigue and the aging on the mechanical properties and the damage development [1-3]. The effect of thermal fatigue (-100°C,+100°C) and thermal aging (250h, 400h at110°C) on mechanical performance of carbon fiber/RTM6 resin and carbon fiber/BMI resin composites has been studied in [4]. The crack density is a consequence of damage that either may be caused by thermal fatigue or degradation due to matrix or interface aging. Previous studies have shown that the high temperature is important in determining the damage level during thermal cycling [5, 6]. Although at high temperature the material is close to the stress free state, it is under severe conditions to develop more damage due to degradation during exposure to high temperatures. Possible reasons are the degradation of the polymer network leading to deteriorated resin properties. This effect can be intensified and accelerated at higher pressures [7] which can also lead to a decrease in the tensile shear strength. The degradation may also be identified by the weight loss either after thermal cycling or after isothermal aging [8, 9]. It has been demonstrated that the isothermally aged woven composite made of carbon fiber/epoxy loses more weight than the thermally-cycled specimens throughout the entire range of the equivalent cycle time at around 180°C. This was explained by the volumetric relaxation of the polymer matrix after

each cycle and by the diffusion rate of oxygen through the epoxy matrix during thermal cycling, which is considerably lower than the diffusion rate at isothermal condition. Another study showed that the aging time of carbon fiber/epoxy (IMS/977-2) composite (at 217°C) has an effect on its viscoelastic properties [10]. This phenomenon is linked to the effect of molecular degradation on the glass transition temperature. The chemical and physical changes occurring during aging are accompanied by a variation in molecular mobility, the glass transition temperature increases at the beginning of aging followed by a decrease which was the evidence of degradation of the resin due to chain rupture.

It becomes clear that the matrix is very important, as this constituent dictates the material's response at high temperature. The degradation of neat polyimide resin and CF/polyimide composite at (320°C, 360°C) was studied in [11]. The authors have proved that the composite weight loss comes only from the matrix degradation and thus the carbon fibers have good thermal oxidation resistance. The choice of the appropriate resin is the most complicated issue for the high temperature composites. A description of the development of high temperature polymeric composites is given in [12]. The commonly used epoxy, which reached the limit of service temperature above 135°C, was replaced by polyimide resin used as polymer matrices in composites for service temperatures between 250°C and 350°C.

In the current work the objective is to study the thermal stability of quasi-isotropic CF/polyimide composite by analyzing the micro-cracks due to thermal fatigue loading or to isothermal aging at 288°C.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials description

The composite material studied in this paper is designated for severe operating conditions; it has a potential in aero-engine application. It is a quasi-isotropic laminate [(+45/-45)/(90/0)]_{2s} prepared using 8-harness satin weave based on Cytec T650 carbon fibers and thermosetting polyimide resin denoted NEXIMID® MHT-R (MHT-R). The resin is a low molecular weight phenylethynyl terminated polyimide (PETI) resin that contains a combination of 4-(Phenylethynyl)Phthalic Anhydride (4-PEPA), end-group cross-linker and ethynyl bis-phthalic anhydride (EBPA) main chain cross-linker. The use of optimized combinations of the 4-PEPA and EBPA (both Nexamide™ type) is expected to enable ultimate T_g above 400°C.

The samples were cut from two different plates labeled 432 and 433. These plates were manufactured at Swerea SICOMP, Piteå using resin transfer moulding (RTM) and cured at 340°C for 30min followed by 2.5h post cure at 370°C. The plate 432 is composed of (Sigmatec T650 8H satin as reinforcement and MHT-R as matrix). In the plate 433, the same reinforcement was used. Whereas, the MHT-R resin was mixed with 4% of A57, which is a reactive diluent acting to lower the viscosity during processing. Both plates were demolded at 70°C and cooled down to 0°C for 2 hours.

The fibers volume fraction is around 60%; the T_g is between 350°C and 400°C; the uncured resin melts between 200°C and 250°C and the cross-linking happens above 320°C. A brief idea about the mechanical properties of the quasi-isotropic laminate is given below:

E Tensile ≈ 48GPa / E Compression ≈ 45GPa

Tensile strength ≈ 471 MPa / Compression strength ≈ 371 MPa

The thickness of the laminate is 2,9mm.

2.2 Experimental procedures

Two groups of specimens were cut from each plate. The first group was divided in two subgroups and subjected to two different thermal cycling loading sequences. The first ramp (R1) was between -60°C and room temperature (RT) whereas the second ramp (R2) was between -60°C and 288°C. The specimens were exposed 10 minutes to each temperature and were subjected to up to 150 cycles.

The second group of specimens was subjected to isothermal loading at 288°C for up to 960 hours.

After the cutting a fine polishing was performed until it was possible to see the fibers section clearly with microscope. The thermal stability was characterized by following the micro-cracks evolution by means of optical microscopy. After certain number of cycles or certain number of aging

hours, the respective number of cracks was counted in each layer separately and the crack density was calculated as the number of cracks per unit length in each layer.

The mesostructure and the damage state of all the specimens were analyzed under microscope before any treatment. Some examples are presented in (Fig.1). Due to thermal residual stresses coming only from manufacturing, some cracks appeared in the bundles with different densities resumed in (Fig.2). The first observation that can be done is that the density of the outer +45_layer cracks is much higher comparing to the rest of bundles; it is negligible for the ± 45 _layers. Most of the 90_layer cracks in plate 432 start from voids. The void content was measured through the area fraction in 100mm^2 of the edge surface of the material. From one specimen to another, the void content varied from 0,31% to 2,36% in 432. The void content in the plate 433 was almost zero. It seems that the void content is not so high; however, the voids were not uniformly distributed in the material. In an area of $1,15\text{mm}^2$, the voids content went from 0% to 13% in 432. It is also important to mention that the scatter was bigger in the specimens cut close to the edges of the plate. The comparably large variation in porosity was related to manufacturing specific details.

Figure1: Cracks caused by the residual stresses.

Figure2: Crack density on the “untreated” specimens (a) plate 432 and (b) plate 433.

In (Fig.2), the specimens labeled with the lower index are cut closer to the edges of the plate. The previous description also explains why higher crack density in the 90-layer was obtained in the specimens cut from the middle of the plate.

Despite the absence of voids in the plate 433, and contrarily to the expectations, it had approximately as many cracks as the other plates. That can potentially be related to the composition of its matrix which seems to become more brittle when mixed with the diluent.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal fatigue results

After certain number of steps of thermal loading, one specimen was saved and the number of cracks was counted along 53mm on both edges. The numbers plotted in (Fig.3) are the average of two edges on one specimen. First, the damage resulting from each thermal loading ramp can be compared. For all the orientations, it is clear that R2 (-60°C to 288°C) induced more damage than R1 (-60°C to RT). One can think that 288°C is close to the stress free temperature, so less damage could be expected, however, it revealed that the interval between the minimum and maximum temperature has more effect on the crack initiation in thermal fatigue.

If we compare both plates, there is no clear decision to choose which plate is thermally more stable than the other. R1 and R2 are causing opposite results on the plates...

Matching the discussion in the previous section, the Outer +45_layers are developing almost double amount of cracks comparing to the inner layers. The inner +45_layers and -45_layers are showing the same behavior, thus the decision to consider them as same orientation and the average of crack density was taken on all the 45s layers on both edges. It appears that those layers developed approximately the same amount of cracks as in the 90_layers at the end of the thermal loading (after 150 cycles) which is in agreement with the quasi-isotropic stacking sequence. However, the damage in the 45_layers starts later than in 90_layers. (Fig.4) presents the crack density distribution along the thickness of one 432 specimen after 150 cycles in R2.

Figure3: Comparison between the effect of R1 and R2 on both plates

Figure4: Crack density distribution in the layers along 432 specimen's thickness.

It was investigated whether the observed cracks are propagate inside the specimens or are only an edge effect. The results presented in (Fig.5) where the specimen subjected to 150 cycles with R2 was polished down from the edge first until d1=0.9mm and then until d2=2.4mm, where d is the distance from the edge of the specimen. The crack density stays significant after the polishing even if it decreases a bit.

Figure5: Crack density inside the thermally cycled specimen.

3.2 Aging results

The crack density versus the number of hours that the specimens were exposed to 288°C is presented in (Fig.6), two specimens from each plate were tested. The cracks initiated during the cooling down to room temperature. The counting was performed after 24 hours from taking them from the oven. Before any thermal treatment the outer +45_layers present the highest crack density, during the aging the crack density of the 90_layer is increasing in an accelerated rate comparing to the outer +45_layer, the crack density in the inside ±45_layers initiated later, after around 500 hours of aging time. Those cracks are all counted on the edges of the specimens; they are definitely not saturated (the crack density is rather low).

Figure6: Crack density versus aging time.

The polishing of one 40 days aged specimen (433_2) was performed in order to investigate the cracks inside the laminate as it was done for a thermally cycled specimen (see Fig.7). The results are different; the 90_layer cracks are abundant only in the edge since they disappeared inside the laminate, but they are not less than the 90_layer cracks that was found in the same sample before any treatment (only from residual thermal stresses after the manufacturing). The crack density in the +45_layers and the -45_layers remains the same and in some cases increases specially after the second polishing.

Figure7: Crack density inside a 40days aged specimen (433-2).

In the thermal fatigue loading, two effects contributed to the damage of the material, the effect of possible fatigue during cycling and the effect of aging which is occurring due to the time spent at high temperature. A comparison was done (Fig.8) by aging two samples at 288°C during the equivalent aging time in the thermal fatigue which is the 10 minutes spent during each loading step multiplied by the number of cycles (150 cycles). We found out that the specimens aged only for 25h presented less

cracks that the specimens subjected to additional loading, which confirms our hypothesis. If the same specimen was additionally 10 minutes in liquid nitrogen (-60°C), the crack density increases slightly.

Figure8: Comparison between aging and thermal cycling effects.

The long exposure to high temperature at an oxidative atmosphere generally leads to degradation of the material and thus a weight loss. An average of weight loss taken over 4 specimens from each plate is plotted versus the aging hours is (Fig.9). The weight loss did not exceed the 1.6% after 40 days of aging at 288°C. This is evidence that this material is a good candidate for high temperature applications.

Figure9: Weight loss due to aging at 288°C.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Micro-damage evolution in two quasi-isotropic CF/polyimide composites for high temperature applications, with different resin composition, was investigated showing two phenomena contributing to damage resistance reduction.

Firstly, the increasing crack density during thermal cycling was studied showing that the highest temperature in the cycle which has the lowest thermal stress level is of primary importance for damage developments. To separate the fatigue effects from possible material aging effects during the total time at high temperature, a separate group of specimens was aged for the time equal to the total time at the same highest temperature as in the cycling test showing that aging is a part of the total degradation during cyclic loading.

Secondly, the composite failure resistance during aging was analysed using the aging time as a variable. The resistance to cracking reduces with aging time and the crack density after cooling down

to room temperature is increasing. Results show a large edge effect in composite degradation: the number of cracks inside the specimen is much lower.

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